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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
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THE INFLUENCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION ON BUSINESS START-UP INTENTION AMONG FINAL YEAR STUDENTS OF BAUCHI STATE UNIVERSITY: THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SELF-EFFICACY

By

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to examine the influence of entrepreneurial mindset on business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University (BASUG). The study aims to determine the influence of entrepreneurial innovation on business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University. It also aims to find out the influence of entrepreneurial alertness on business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University. This study proposes a conceptual framework based on three variables (entrepreneurial mind set, entrepreneurial innovation and entrepreneurial alertness) with mediating effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in order to examine the influence of entrepreneurial intention on business start-up intention among final year students of Bauchi State University. This research modified planned behavior model. In conclusion, Proper introduction of entrepreneurial education would improve entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial innovation, and entrepreneurial alertness to achieve better business start-up intention in BASUG. The study provides a great foundation for final year students to work on their business startup intention in terms of mindset, innovation and alertness among other related factors that could affect their business performance. For government and other regulatory agencies also, the study draws their attention to the benefit of considering one's entrepreneurial intention when providing entrepreneurial support.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial intention, Business start-up, Entrepreneurial Innovation, Entrepreneurial mind set, Entrepreneurial alertness, Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Few decades ago, research on entrepreneurial activities has attracted attention of researchers in various fields of study such as psychology, sociology, and business administration. This is due to the importance of entrepreneurship in the growth and development of any nation. In any developing economy, the role of entrepreneurial activities in achieving sustainable economic growth and development cannot be over-emphasized. Entrepreneurship has been considered as an engine growth for economic development. Thus, it has conquered the cardinal theme of academics and the interest governmental policy makers (Muhammad, 2019; Kaegon & Nwogu, 2019).

To understand the importance of the phenomenon, first, we have to examine the background of the study. The challenges currently faced by most developing countries in the world includes how to ensure their large youth populations are gainfully employed. The growing rate of unemployment among young graduates, due to delays in finding jobs that align with their professions and expectations, has become a major focus of intense deliberation for both academics and managers. Therefore, this research study focuses on entrepreneurial Innovation, entrepreneurial mind set, entrepreneurial alertness, and entrepreneurial self-efficacy as the mediating variable to examine the influences of entrepreneurial intention on business start-up intention among final year students of Bauchi State University.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Despite all the efforts put together to create awareness on starting up a business among the final year students, there are rising concerns over the state of unemployment in Nigeria. With the population of over 219 million, Nigeria is among the highly populated countries in the world. It ranks as the 7th country by population according to United Nation estimate (United Nation, 2023). 64% of the population are youths and unemployed graduates are over 44.1%. The percentage of graduates without jobs is rapidly rising. Universities and polytechnics enroll almost 2 million students yearly and graduate around 600,000. (The Nigerian graduate Report 2022). The Nigeria government has been formulated different policies and launched different incentive programmes to ease employment problem. Governments are trying to support and

encourage young people especially final year students to be self employed by establishing their own businesses. This initiative aims to create more jobs, thereby positively impacting the reduction of the unemployment problem.

The government and people of Nigeria are having substantial worries about the poor state which entrepreneurship finds itself in Nigeria. One of the major challenges associated with Nigerian education is the inability of the colleges and universities to prepare graduates and students to be entrepreneurs or to be self-reliant (Asaju, Arome, & Anyio, 2019). Even though it is expected that these students have been taught and have also acquired some skills necessary to startup their own businesses after graduation, it is surprising that the problem of unemployment continue to rise among young graduates in Nigeria. This status quo seems to be a threat to the goals and objectives of starting up a new business among final year students in Nigeria. Therefore, creating opportunities become very important for people to strive and set up their business in order to be self-reliant.

This research paper will bridge methodological gap by introducing the mediating effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and evaluate the influence entrepreneurial intention on business start-up intention among final year students of Bauchi State University. However, in line with the managerial issues earlier highlighted and the theoretical and contextual gap that exist in this research, the study seeks to bridge the gap by examining the relationship between the variables; using entrepreneurial mind set, entrepreneurial innovation, entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial self-efficacy as the mediator on business start-up intention among the Bauchi state university final year students in particular.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to provide solution to the above outlined problems.

- i. Does entrepreneurial mind set have significant influence on business startup among final year students?
- ii. Does entrepreneurial innovation have significant influence on business startup among final year students?

- iii. Does entrepreneurial alertness have significant influence on business startup among final year students?
- iv. Does self-efficacy mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial mind set, entrepreneurial innovation, and entrepreneurial alertness on business startup among Bauchi state university final year students?

1.4 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of entrepreneurial intention on business start-up intention among final year students in Bauchi State University. The specific objectives of the study are:

- i. To examine the influence of entrepreneurial mind set on business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University.
- ii. To determine the influence of entrepreneurial innovation on business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University.
- iii. To find out the influence of entrepreneurial alertness on business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University.
- iv. To examine entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between entrepreneurial mind set and business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University.
- v. To examine entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between entrepreneurial innovation and business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University.
- vi. To examine entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and business start-up among final year students of Bauchi State University.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW, EMPIRICAL REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT:

Many research studies were carryout in the area of entrepreneurial intention and business startup intention among students of higher institutions in Nigeria and other developing

countries in the world. Some of them were reviewed by researchers/scholars. Research hypothesis was developed below based on the research findings on the significance of the relationships among different variables.

2.1 ENTREPRENEURIAL MINDSET AND BUSINESS STARTUP INTENTION

Ludi, et al (2020) conducted a research titled "the impact of entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial mindset: the mediating role of attitude and self-efficacy". The main purpose of the research is to investigate the relationship between students' entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial mindset as well as understanding the mediating role of attitude and self-efficacy. The approach adopted in the study is a convenience random sampling method, which is widely used in entrepreneurship research. Participants were recruited from several universities in Malang of East Java in Indonesia undergoing an online survey and were calculated using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The findings of this current study indicate, on one hand, that entrepreneurship education positively influences entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial attitude, and entrepreneurial mindset. On the other hand, entrepreneurial self-efficacy promotes entrepreneurial attitude instead of entrepreneurial mindset. Furthermore, entrepreneurial attitude plays an essential role in mediating both entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy toward students' entrepreneurial mindset.

Based upon these past studies, it is believed that students with entrepreneurial mindsets participate actively in entrepreneurial activities than other individuals. Therefore, hypothesis is developed as the expectation of this research.

H1: There is significant relationship between entrepreneurial mindset and Business startup intention.

2.2. ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND BUSINESS STARTUP INTENTION

Hasan, and Mohammad (2022) conducted a study on the Impact of autonomy, innovativeness, risk-taking, proactiveness, and competitive aggressiveness on student's intention to start a new venture. This study examines the impact of entrepreneurial orientation dimensions on students' intention to start new businesses in Saudi

universities. Using a 21-item questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale, the authors collected data on students' demographics, entrepreneurial orientation, and entrepreneurial behavioural intention. The sample consisted of 341 business students from two public universities in Saudi Arabia. Specifically, business students were chosen for this study because they are considered potential entrepreneurs. Through structural equation modeling, AMOS software was used to analyze the study model. Results showed a strong relationship between entrepreneurial intention and greater autonomy, innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness. In contrast, competitive and aggressive behavior, is not strongly related to entrepreneurial intention. These findings are important because they shed new light on the factors that shape future entrepreneurs, thereby making a significant theoretical contribution to the literature on entrepreneurial orientation, particularly in the context of university business students. As countries embrace the importance of innovation and entrepreneurship in enhancing their global competitiveness, this study also makes a practical contribution to policymakers to identify potential entrepreneurs and transform them into successful ones. Thus, based on the previous research studies, it is argued that individuals who perceived a high level of entrepreneurial innovation are more likely to pursue a career in entrepreneurship. Therefore, this study proposed the following hypotheses.

H₂: There is significant relationship between entrepreneurial Innovation and Business startup intention.

2.3. ENTREPRENEURIAL ALERTNESS AND BUSINESS STARTUP INTENTION

Samo, and Hashim (2019) conducted a study on the Impact of Entrepreneurial Alertness on Entrepreneurial Intentions. The identification of opportunities is based on intentions which are the result of people's belief and way of thinking. Entrepreneurial alertness is considered vital for identifying the opportunity which can have an impact on mindset for exploiting the opportunities. The objective of this study was to analyze the connection between identification of opportunity and formation of intention through entrepreneurial alertness based on the theory of planned behavior. The data was collected from the 499 final year business students of nine universities from Sindh, Pakistan using cross-sectional survey. The results of this study revealed that entrepreneurial alertness has

positive and significant effect on attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control and entrepreneurial intentions. The findings of this study contributed to the theory of planned behavior by taking entrepreneurial alertness as a predictor of entrepreneurial intentions. The findings also have implication for increasing the supply of entrepreneurial capital into the society. Considering the findings of the past studies, it is believed that students with entrepreneurial alertness participate more actively in entrepreneurial activities than other individuals. Therefore, this study proposed the following hypotheses.

H3: There is significant relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and Business startup intention.

2.4. ENTREPRENEURIAL SELF-EFFICACY AND BUSINESS STARTUP INTENTION

Azeem, Hashmi, Imran, and ChikImL (2021) conducted a study titled "Role of entrepreneurial passion and entrepreneurial self-efficacy in developing students' intention to become an entrepreneur: An evidence from Malaysia". Using social cognitive theory as the underpinning theoretical framework, the study aims to examine the role of entrepreneurial passion in influencing entrepreneurial self-efficacy among students that further leads to their intention to become an entrepreneur. Data was collected from the business and economics students of three universities located across Malaysia through a cross-sectional design. The results revealed that entrepreneurial passion positively effects students' intention to launch a new venture after graduation. Whereas entrepreneurial self-efficacy offers an intervening mechanism that links and translates the impact of entrepreneurial passion on students' entrepreneurial intention, the relationship is also moderated by entrepreneurial education. The study thus addresses the call by past researchers on the missing link that unfold into to one's entrepreneurial intention. Findings thereby provides the possible future directions of how person and context factors could leverage individuals' entrepreneurial self-efficacy to facilitate the process to become an entrepreneur. Considering the findings of past studies, it is believed that there is a relationship between the variables, with some studies showing significant relationships and others showing insignificant ones. Therefore, this study proposed the following hypotheses.

H4: Entrepreneurial self-efficacy mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial mind set, entrepreneurial innovation, entrepreneurial alertness and Business startup intention.

2.5 MEDIATING EFFECT OF SELF-EFFICACY:

Among the studied antecedents and constructs, entrepreneurial self-efficacy is known to be the major predictor for individuals to become an entrepreneur (Crespo, Belchior, & Costa, 2018). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy, the belief in one's ability to succeed, is strongly associated with entrepreneurial intention, as it represents the planned and focused actions to become an entrepreneur (Krueger & Brazeal, 2019). Since passionate entrepreneurs are committed to the identification and exploitation of new business opportunities, self-efficacy in that case reinforces and reshapes the beliefs one holds regarding his or her ability to complete the project under consideration and achieve its objective (Nowiński, & Czeglédi, 2019). Because new venture causes individuals to rethink their abilities supported by a strong mindset, a high level of passion also influences one's degree of efficacy and ability to become an entrepreneur (Neuman, W. (2008). There is need to present the mediating effect and test the relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial Innovation, entrepreneurial alertness to business startup intention in line with the recommendation given by Christopher (2020). These actions may altogether cultivate one's strong sense to start or establish a new venture or become a successful entrepreneur. This study recommends entrepreneurial self-efficacy as the mediating factor for the influence of entrepreneurial intention on business start-up intention among final year students of Bauchi State University. Authentication of **H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, and H6**, could show a direct effect of self-efficacy between entrepreneurial intention and Business startup intention among final year students of Bauchi State University. Therefore, based on the aforementioned rationale, the study proposes the following hypotheses.

H1: There is significant relationship between entrepreneurial mindset and Business startup intention.

H2: There is significant relationship between entrepreneurial Innovation and Business startup intention.

H3: There is significant relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and Business startup intention.

H4: The relationship between entrepreneurial mindset and Business startup intention will be mediated by entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

H5: The relationship between entrepreneurial Innovation and Business startup intention will be mediated by entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

H6: The relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and Business startup intention will be mediated by entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

2.6 UNDERPINNING THEORY:

This research study used Planned Behavior TPB by Fishbein & Ajzen (1975) to underpin the variables of this study.

2.6.1 THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR TPB BY (FISHBEIN & AJZEN (1975))

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) which “predicts and explains behaviour in specific contexts” (Ajzen, 1991) is a frequently used theory in different disciplines (Renko, Kroeck, and Bullough, 2019). This is also true for entrepreneurship research since to become an entrepreneur, is considered a conscious activity with intention is seen as a cognitive state (Renko, Kroeck, and Bullough, 2019). As a result, cognition provides more significant information regarding entrepreneurial behavior than personality traits or demographic studies, as it is a 'closer antecedent' to behavior (Liñán, Rodríguez, & Rueda, 2018; Kautonen, Van Gelderen, & Tornikoski, 2013). The outcomes of the previous work also suggested that theory of planned behaviour is applicable to entrepreneurial research (Liñán, 2018). Consequently, intention-oriented research within the entrepreneurship literature are gaining popularity.

For infrequent behaviours/unstable contexts (which is true for entrepreneurial context), the explanatory power of intention regarding behaviour is increased (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000, Engle, et al 2018). It is argued that strategic entrepreneurship is taken to be an intentionally planned behaviour, and this is true for even necessity motivated and unexpected entrepreneurship (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000). Therefore, this research, which studies the influence of entrepreneurial intention on business start-up

intention among final year students of Bauchi State University will be processed via theory of planned behaviour (TPB) as suggested by Liñán (2018).

There are two known attitudes for individuals that are intuitive and rational (Barbosa, Gerhardt, & Kickul, 2017), and the main assumption for Ajzen's intention-behaviour relation is that human behaviour is rational (Kor, & Mullan, 2018). Intention refers to the degree to which a behavior is intended to be attempted, along with the effort put forth for this behavior (Ajzen, 1991). The stronger the intention, the greater the likelihood of the behavior being realized (Kor & Mullan, 2018). Intention provides a link between an individual's beliefs and corresponding behavior (Boyd & Vozikis, 1994). This is particularly typical in entrepreneurial contexts, although the new business start-up process may evolve suddenly due to opportunity realization (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000).

According to TPB, there are two major sources of intention: desirability (motivation to act for the intended behaviour) and feasibility of the given behaviour (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000). To be more precise, perceived behavioural control (PBC) stands for feasibility; subjective norms and personal attitude towards entrepreneurial behaviour together define the desirability part of the entrepreneurial intention. These are three kinds of conceptually independent (Doll, & Ajzen, 1992) beliefs which are behavioural, normative and control beliefs, respectively (Ajzen, 2002). Although this model is a generic one that holds across cultures and contexts, the relative importance of the factors may change (Ajzen, 2002). In generic form, intention may increase when there is a positive attitude towards the behaviour. Subjective norms regarding the behaviour is favourable and individual has a belief that he/she can accomplish the behaviour effectively (Carr, & Sequeira, 2007).

Fig. 1

The framework of planned behaviour theory provides a good and better understanding of entrepreneurial intention and Business startup intention (Carr, & Sequeira, 2018).

Subjective norms (SN) represents the perception of significant others about a given behaviour. The main assumption for adding this factor to the model is the argument that human behaviour is adopted according to another people's attitude towards given behaviour (Norman, Conner, & Bell, 2000). Although the effect is taken to be effectual across cases and cultures, the significant others differ for different individuals. For instance, for individuals holding a job, the co-workers or other work-related networks are important. On the other hand, for students, family and friends may be important. The effect of subjective norms within the model is questioned due to insignificant and non-systematic previous results regarding it. However, it is argued that, when intention is measured appropriately, there appears a strong relation between norms and intention (Armitage, & Conner, 2001). By definition, regarding this factor, the belief of others is weighed by individuals' readiness and willingness to act according to these beliefs (Krueger, Norris, 2000).

2.6.2 Conceptual Framework:

Fig 2.

Sources: Norzahidah, and Kamariah (2020) Abdullahi, and Sulaiman, (2020)

3.1. CONCLUSION:

This study proposes a conceptual framework based on three variables (entrepreneurial mind set, entrepreneurial innovation and entrepreneurial alertness) with mediating effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in order to examine the influences of entrepreneurial intention on business start-up intention among final year students of Bauchi State University. This research modified planned behavior model. This study adds knowledge to the existing literature towards understanding the determinants that lead to Business start up among final years students of Bauchi State University. This conceptual model should serve as a guide to researchers who wish to conduct additional empirical studies on the relationship presented in the model.

3.2. RECOMMENDATIONS:

The University administrators may provide workshop sessions necessary to enrich the practical of entrepreneurship skills and keep ensuring that there are learning resources to support active learning, interaction, and collaboration among students. The students may be encouraged to attend entrepreneurship courses so that they will be able to acquire the necessary skills and develop their intention and self-efficacy to put up their venture in the future. To assess the effects of self-efficacy and entrepreneurship education on learners' entrepreneurial intention, future studies may employ additional types of qualitative data. This would make correlating the data more tangible. For government and other regulatory agencies also, this study draws their attention to the benefit of considering one's entrepreneurial intention when providing entrepreneurial support.

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